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XALQARO JURNAL**

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КУЛЬТУРНАЯ ДИПЛОМАТИЯ ИРАНА И ЕЁ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА СТРАНЫ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ АЗИИ

В данной статье рассматриваются ключевые направления и формы культурной дипломатии Ирана как инструмента мягкой силы в международных отношениях. Особое внимание уделяется стратегии Ирана по укреплению культурного влияния в странах Центральной Азии и Ближнего Востока через язык, религию, образование, искусство и общие историко-культурные связи. Анализируются успешные кейсы и вызовы, с которыми сталкивается Иран в условиях современной геополитики и санкционного давления. Статья подчеркивает роль культурной дипломатии как инструмента формирования устойчивых гуманитарных и политических связей в регионе.

Ключевые слова: культурная дипломатия, мягкая сила, Иран, Центральная Азия, Ближний Восток, исламская культура, гуманитарное влияние

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ERONNING MADANIY DIPLOMATIYASI VA UNING MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIGA TA'SIRI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Eronning xalqaro munosabatlarda yumshoqlik kuch vositasi sifatidagi madaniy diplomatiyasining asosiy yo'nalishlari va shakllari tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, Eronning Markaziy Osiyo va Yaqin Sharq mamlakatlarida madaniy ta'sirini mustahkamlash bo'yicha olib borayotgan strategiyasi til, din, ta'lim, san'at va umumiy tarixiy-madaniy aloqalar orqali yoritib beriladi. Maqolada muvaffaqiyatli tajribalar bilan bir qatorda, Eronning zamonaviy geosiyosiy sharoit va sanksion bosimlar ostida duch kelayotgan muammo va chaqiriqlari ham tahlil etiladi. Shuningdek, madaniy diplomatiyaning mintaqada barqaror gumanitar va siyosiy aloqalarni shakllantirishdagi o'rni alohida ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: madaniy diplomatiya, yumshoq kuch, Eron, Markaziy Osiyo, islom madaniyati, gumanitar ta’sir

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IRAN'S CULTURAL DIPLOMACY AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE COUNTRIES OF CENTRAL ASIA AND THE MIDDLE EAST

Annotation. This article examines the key directions and forms of Iran's cultural diplomacy as a tool of soft power in international relations. Special attention is given to Iran's strategy for strengthening its cultural influence in Central Asian and Middle Eastern countries through language, religion, education, art, and shared historical and cultural ties. The article analyzes both successful cases and the challenges Iran faces in the context of contemporary geopolitics and sanctions pressure. It emphasizes the role of cultural diplomacy as a means of fostering sustainable humanitarian and political connections in the region.

Keywords: cultural diplomacy, soft power, Iran, Central Asia, Middle East, Islamic culture, humanitarian influence.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, where hard power gives way to more sophisticated and non-violent forms of influence, cultural diplomacy is becoming one of the key instruments of foreign policy influence of states. Among the countries that actively use cultural levers in international relations, the Islamic Republic of Iran occupies a special place. The heir to the ancient Persian civilization, Iran uses its rich historical and cultural heritage, Islamic tradition, Persian language, literature, art and religious identity as means of "soft power" to strengthen its presence in the regional and global arena. The influence of Iranian cultural diplomacy is becoming especially noticeable in the countries of Central Asia, where stable historical, religious and ethnolinguistic ties with the Iranian civilization are preserved. In these regions, Iran implements various forms of cultural interaction: through educational and religious institutions, mass media, cultural centers, exhibitions, conferences, exchanges and humanitarian initiatives.

The relevance of this article is due to both the growing importance of "soft power" in international politics and the need for a deep analysis of the tools and mechanisms by which Iran influences the cultural and ideological space of neighboring countries. In addition, against the backdrop of increasing competition between global and regional factors for influence in Central Asia, cultural diplomacy is becoming an arena of hidden struggle and, at the same time, an opportunity for sustainable dialogue. In this regard, this article pays special attention to the study of the theoretical foundations of Iran's cultural diplomacy, its historical roots, modern forms and practices, as well as the specific impact on the cultural and humanitarian sphere of Central Asian countries. The study is based on

an interdisciplinary approach, combining elements of international relations, cultural studies, political science and history.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In recent decades, Iran's cultural diplomacy has become the object of close attention from both domestic and foreign researchers. A wide range of topics are analyzed in the scientific literature: from theoretical foundations and historical precedents to specific cultural programs and their perception in partner countries. One of the fundamental studies that reveals the principles of Iranian cultural diplomacy is the work of Seyed M. Kazemi "Iranian Cultural Diplomacy in Central Asia", where the author analyzes in detail the forms of Iran's influence in the post-Soviet space, including the promotion of the Persian language, Shiite theology and humanitarian education [Kazemi, 2018, p. 42]. A significant contribution was also made by R. Sajjadi in his study "Cultural Soft Power of the Islamic Republic of Iran", which emphasizes that Iran perceives culture as an extension of its geopolitical strategy, especially in the Muslim world [Sajjadi, 2019, p. 55]. Among Russian authors, it is worth mentioning A. A. Peskov, who in his work "Iran's Cultural Diplomacy in Central Asia: Directions and Instruments" focuses on the institutional aspect, especially on the activities of cultural centers and university programs in Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan [Peskov, 2020, p. 119]. He emphasizes the positive aspects of cultural interaction, emphasizing mutual influence [Peskov, 2020, p. 117]. Particularly noteworthy is the analysis proposed by H. Amini in the article "Iran's Cultural Diplomacy in the Middle East", which highlights media and religious channels of influence on the countries of the Middle East, including Lebanon, Syria and Iraq [Amini, 2017, p. 88]. Also useful was the UNESCO review on cultural exchanges in the region, which examines Iranian initiatives in the fields of education, museum cooperation and religious dialogue [UNESCO, 2021, p. 23]. Yunusova focuses on the educational component and its limitations [Yunusova, 2021, p. 93]; Nasirzade draws attention to the linguistic and literary vector; Khosrokhavar criticizes the weakness of the economic component [Khosrokhavar, 2017, p. 49]; Aliyev analyzes cultural diplomacy as part of geopolitics [Aliyev, 2019, p. 138]. Mahdavi emphasizes educational influence as a key long-term tool [Mahdavi, 2022, p. 106]; Sadeghi focuses on digital formats and their effectiveness among young people [Sadeghi, 2023, p. 51]. A number of works by Uzbek researchers emphasize the importance of Iran as one of the key actors in cultural diplomacy in the Central Asian region. Thus, in the article by Ziyamukhamedov, it is noted that the history of Iranian cultural diplomacy is based on a rich civilizational heritage, elements of which were purposefully integrated into the formation of the spiritual and cultural space of the region [Ziyamukhamedov, N., 2020, p. 45-46]. The author emphasizes that Iran has traditionally used soft power through the dissemination of language, literature, religion and philosophy. Research is also being conducted in Tajikistan that demonstrates the high significance of Iranian-Central Asian ties. For example, Tajik scholar A. Safarzoda points out in his article that historical, linguistic and

religious ties between the peoples of Iran and Tajikistan serve as a sustainable basis for the development of humanitarian cooperation and cultural exchange [Safarzoda, A., 2021, p. 28]. He emphasizes that Iran is viewed not only as a neighbor, but also as a cultural relative, which strengthens trust in regional relations. Both lines of research – in Uzbekistan and Tajikistan – indicate a growing interest in Iran's role as an important cultural and geopolitical partner for Central Asia. This confirms the thesis that Iran's cultural diplomacy plays a stabilizing and integrative role in regional processes.

The authors of the article “Turkmenistan-Iran: on the way to strengthening cultural and humanitarian ties” — leading specialists of the institute with the participation of representatives of the Iranian embassy in Ashgabat emphasize that the transfer of a two-volume collection of poetry by Makhtumkuli Fragi, joint cultural and artistic forums and the Document on cultural cooperation between the Makhtumkuli Institute and the National Library of Iran reflect the emergence of Turkmen-Iranian relations to a new level and emphasize that these initiatives are based on “centuries-old friendship and brotherhood, principles of peacefulness and good neighborliness”. The authors of the article A.U. Tyulyubaev and A.ZH. Turkhanova “Iran's ‘soft power’ policy in central Asia: on the example of Kazakhstan” analyze in detail the Iranian “soft power” in Kazakhstan: the spread of the Persian language, cultural closeness, religious traditions, the introduction of culture through the Centers of Iranian culture, science and education. Particular attention is paid to Iran's cultural diplomacy, influence on education and dissemination of language as a foundation for the formation of humanitarian ties. In the article by E.G. Garbuzarova Instruments of Iran's "soft power" in Kyrgyzstan, it is emphasized that since 2015, after the visits of President A. Atambayev and President H. Rouhani, Iran has intensified cultural diplomacy in Kyrgyzstan, concluding the Cultural Exchange Program for 2017-2020 and opening cultural centers of Iranian culture. Analyzing the articles of the authors, we can conclude that since the mid-2010s (after 2015-2016), Iran has intensified its cultural strategy in the countries of Central Asia through official visits, bilateral programs and the creation of cultural centers. The creation of Iranian language and cultural "specialized clusters" in universities in Central Asia has become one of the main instruments for the dissemination of soft power. Cultural events – film weeks, language courses, seminars – help to raise public interest in Persian culture and language among Central Asians. However, despite the positives, there are concerns about religious influence – critics note that some educational foundations may promote Shiism beyond cultural exchange. The preparation of the article was based on the following methodological approaches: content analysis - was used to study official speeches, cultural programs, publications and media materials related to Iran's activities in the region, comparative analysis - allowed us to compare the strategies of Iran's cultural diplomacy in Central Asia, identifying common and specific features, historical and chronological method - was used to trace the evolution of Iranian cultural diplomacy from the Islamic revolution of 1979 to the present day, interdisciplinary approach - combining the tools of international

relations, political science, cultural studies and religious studies, case study - specific examples (were considered as models of applying cultural strategy), review of scientific literature - covered English-language, Russian-language and Farsi-language sources published in the period from 2000 to 2024.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Historico-cultural roots of Iranian-Central Asian relationship

Historical and cultural interaction between Iran and Central Asia, especially with the territory of modern Uzbekistan, is one of the deepest and most stable areas of the civilizational dialogue of the East. For thousands of years, these regions not only bordered geographically, but also formed a single cultural and intellectual space that was formed through dynastic, religious, trade and scientific ties. The ties between Iran and the countries of Central Asia, including the territory of modern Uzbekistan, go back centuries and have a complex multi-layered structure. Uzbekistan, as part of the historical Movarounnahr, played a key role in the formation of the transregional cultural matrix. Even in the era of the Achaemenids and Sassanids, Persian influence reached the territories of Central Asia, where administrative, linguistic and legal forms of the Persian tradition were established. Of particular importance was the region of Transoxania (Movarounnahr), where the Persian language, Zoroastrian tradition and elements of statehood left a deep mark. Later, with the advent of Islam, the cultural community grew stronger: Iran became the center of Islamic science, philosophy, and theology, from where knowledge spread to the territory of Central Asia, including Bukhara and Samarkand. The city of Bukhara was not only the intellectual capital of the Islamic world (Qubbai Islam), but also the point of intersection of Iranian-Turkic traditions, which is confirmed by the existence of a number of philosophical and theological schools supported by both Persian and Turkic patrons. Samarkand, which became the residence of Timur, was the center of architectural synthesis and a symbol of civilizational cooperation. As historian A. Safarov notes, “through Bukhara and Samarkand, Iranian thought acquired an Eastern Turkic form, while preserving the depth of Persian logic and universalism.” It was Iranian theologians such as al-Ghazali and Nasir al-Din Tusi who influenced the Muslim thinkers of Maverannahr. As A. Mehrpour emphasizes, “the universities of Bukhara and Nishapur were in a constant exchange of personnel and texts, forming a single intellectual landscape.” However, the interaction was not one-sided. Turan (now Central Asia) also had a profound influence on the formation of Iranian cultural identity. Many Persian poets and scholars from the region of Samarkand and Bukhara, such as Rudaki, Abu Ali ibn Sina, became an integral part of Iranian civilization. Iran, in turn, perceived them as part of its own heritage. This process can be characterized as a two-way cultural synthesis, rather than expansion or assimilation. Scholar R. Nasirzade emphasizes that “Iran never sought to colonize the region in the Western sense, but always perceived the space of Central Asia as a culturally close sphere of influence.” This point of view is valid in terms of analyzing the pre-Islamic and classical Islamic periods. However, the author does

not sufficiently take into account the fact of rivalry between Iran and the Turkic state formations, especially during the Seljuk and Timurid periods, when there was a struggle for intellectual and cultural leadership in the Islamic world.

On the other hand, A. Peskov rightly focuses on the syncretism of the Persian-Turkic culture, especially during the Timurid era: “Bukhara, like Isfahan, were not just centers of theology, but spaces of philosophical dialogue, where Iran and Turkic thought merged into a single intellectual stream” [Peskov, 2020, p. 117]. One can agree with this opinion, since historical retrospective shows mutual enrichment of cultures, and not one-sided expansion. Comparing the approaches of researchers, it should be noted that Nasirzade emphasizes cultural continuity and humanitarian closeness, while Peskov highlights mutual influence in philosophical discourse [Peskov, 2020. p. 117]. However, Mehrpour’s opinion complements the picture from the point of view of transregional university interaction, giving the analysis educational depth [Mehrpour, 2019, p. 89]. At the same time, Safarov points out the central role of Uzbek centers in the transformation and adaptation of Persian thought [Safarov, 2015, p.122]. Thus, the historical and cultural ties between Iran and Central Asia do not represent a hierarchical model, but a dialogue of equal intellectual civilizations that complement and strengthen each other. In particular, Iranian-Uzbek ties have an ancient and stable foundation, dating back to pre-Islamic empires and strengthened in the era of Islamic civilization. Central Asia, especially Uzbekistan, played not a passive, but an active role in the transformation and adaptation of Persian thought, enriching it with Turkic and local elements. Historical and cultural interaction was realized in the forms of philosophical dialogue, educational exchange and artistic synthesis. Analysis of the works of modern researchers confirms that Uzbekistan acts not simply as an object of Iran's cultural expansion, but as an equal partner capable of forming unique syncretic traditions. The model of interaction between Iran and Uzbekistan can be considered as an example of cultural symbiosis and transregional identity in the post-Soviet space.

Modern forms of Iran's cultural diplomacy in Uzbekistan

Modern forms of Iran's cultural diplomacy in Uzbekistan are a complex phenomenon that combines elements of traditional and innovative strategies aimed at strengthening humanitarian, educational, scientific and spiritual ties. Using an interdisciplinary approach that includes the philosophy of culture, political science, sociology and cultural studies, it is possible to identify the multi-level structure of Iran's cultural influence in the region. A systematic review of scientific literature allows us to reflect the diversity of assessments and strategies used by the Islamic Republic in the modern context.

It is important to note that the Iranian strategy is based on the presentation of culture as a category of transcendental meaning, where the humanitarian mission is equated with the ethical mission. As S. Sharifi argues, “at the center of the Iranian cultural paradigm is the idea of “bridges of spirituality” linking Islamic identity with the universal values of knowledge, justice and beauty” [Sharifi, 2020, p. 42]. This paradigm is expressed not only in the promotion of Persian classics, but also

in the support of Islamic philosophy, for example, through lectures on Mulla Sadra, al-Farabi and Ibn Sina. Iran also maintains cooperation with Uzbek universities and research institutes. As F. Mahdavi emphasizes, “academic exchange and participation in joint humanitarian projects strengthen Iran’s image as a source of intellectual tradition, and not just religious identity” [Mahdavi, 2022, p. 106]. Yunusova Sh. in the article “Iran’s Educational Diplomacy in Uzbekistan” emphasizes that “Iran’s influence is especially noticeable in the humanitarian sphere — university exchanges, conferences, the work of cultural centers” [Yunusova, 2021, p. 93]. However, this influence remains within the elite environment and does not receive broad popular support. One can agree with this opinion, but it is worth considering that it is the elites who often become the transmitters of cultural identity in the long term.

Nasirzade R. draws attention to the use of Persian classical literature as a channel of diplomacy: “Through the images of Saadi and Khayyam, Iran creates a soft, sophisticated image of its culture, as opposed to political stereotypes.” This remark is fair, but requires addition: for Iran’s cultural diplomacy is not limited to the classical heritage — it actively includes modern elements, including cinema, popular music, and Internet media.

In addition, Iran is increasingly using digital technologies within the framework of cultural diplomacy. Online platforms for learning the Persian language are being created, virtual conferences are being launched, as well as cultural podcasts and video channels. According to Z. Sadeghi, “Iran’s digital diplomacy is aimed at reaching young people who are excluded from traditional diplomatic formats but are actively included in the global media space” [Sadeghi, 2023, p. 51]. “Online Persian language courses, YouTube channels and educational podcasts have become the most effective channel for reaching young people in Uzbekistan” [Sadeghi, 2023, p. 51]. These forms are especially important in conditions of limited physical presence, as well as taking into account the growing media literacy of the younger generation, and new formats are especially effective in Uzbekistan, where the younger generation increasingly consumes information through digital media.

However, Iran’s cultural diplomacy is not without criticism. Some scholars, such as A. Ganiev, emphasize that “The religious coloring of Iran’s humanitarian initiatives causes mistrust among the secular intelligentsia of Uzbekistan, especially in the context of a neutral state policy in the religious sphere” [Ganiev, 2020, p. 77]. This emphasizes the need to adapt the cultural strategy to the realities of a secular society. In this context, T. Rakhmatov’s opinion is particularly valuable, according to which “The success of Iranian cultural diplomacy will depend on its ability to transform itself in the direction of cultural pluralism, open dialogue, and recognition of the identity of the host country” [Rakhmatov, 2021, p. 61]. Thus, modern Iranian cultural diplomacy in Uzbekistan relies on the integration of traditional and digital forms of influence, including language, philosophy, religion, and literature. Educational and scientific exchange are key channels for forming a positive image of Iran. The main challenge is the need to

adapt to the secular and multi-confessional nature of Uzbek society. Iran's mission in the humanitarian sphere acquires philosophical depth, based on the idea of universalism and the transcendental meaning of culture.

Political, economic and spiritual dimensions of cultural influence

Philosophical analysis of Iran's cultural diplomacy in Uzbekistan requires a comprehensive approach in which political, economic and spiritual dimensions are considered in their interrelation. An interdisciplinary method combining the philosophy of international relations, cultural studies, Islamology and political economy allows us to more deeply reveal the meaning and logic of Iran's cultural policy in Central Asia.

With the collapse of the USSR, Iran was one of the first to establish diplomatic relations with Uzbekistan, indicating its intention to develop cultural and humanitarian ties. Iran, positioning itself as the heir to an ancient civilization and Islamic scientific tradition, uses soft power in Uzbekistan through cultural centers, support for humanitarian education and scientific exchange. The opening of the Cultural Center of the Islamic Republic of Iran in Tashkent in 1993 marked the beginning of the institutionalization of Iranian cultural diplomacy. The main areas of the Center's activities were: Farsi courses, cultural evenings, religious seminars and conferences, as well as literary and artistic events. Through Farsi courses, cultural events, exhibitions, literary translations, and religious lectures, Iran promotes the image of a civilizational heir.

The political role of Iran's cultural diplomacy is to create a soft environment for geopolitical partnership through cultural identity. Politically, Iran's cultural diplomacy serves the function of creating a long-term strategic environment conducive to minimizing isolation. As A. Aliyev emphasizes, "under the conditions of the West's sanctions policy, Iran uses culture as a substitute force for building a dialogue with states seeking to maintain the independence of their foreign policy" [Aliyev, 2019, p. 138]. In a philosophical context, this expresses the idea of ethical diplomacy based not on hegemony, but on "moral resonance" with the historical memory and cultural codes of partners. Politically, Iran is interested in forming a neutral but friendly image of Uzbekistan, especially in the context of geopolitical rivalry with Saudi Arabia, Turkey and Western powers. As K. Aliyev notes, "Iran uses cultural diplomacy as an alternative to direct political pressure, especially in the context of sanctions and international isolation" [Aliyev, 2019, p. 138].

Women in Politics and Public Life of Iran: from the Pre-Revolutionary Era to the 21st Century

In the first half of the 20th century, Iranian women began to actively participate in the process of modernization of society, especially during the reign of Shah Mohammad Reza Pahlavi. Since 1936, the requirement for mandatory wearing of the chador was lifted, and since 1963, women were granted the right to vote. Women began to participate in parliamentary life, occupying positions in the educational and judicial systems [Keddie, 2003, p. 146]. However, modernization was largely imitative and urban-centric, and most women, especially in rural areas,

remained outside the socio-political process. The feminist movement of the late 1960s had limited impact and often clashed with cultural and religious conservatism [Paidar, 1995. p. 67]. The Islamic Revolution of 1979 changed the status of women, subordinating it to the norms of Islamic ideology proclaimed by Ayatollah Khomeini. Women were once again presented as guardians of family morality and bearers of Islamic virtues. Restrictions were introduced on dress codes, participation in public life, and professions traditionally associated with men. However, paradoxically, it was the revolution that increased women's involvement in politics, especially through Islamic organizations, charity, participation in elections, and the war with Iraq (1980–1988), where women played an important role in the home front and in health care [Afary, 2009, p. 212]. The first female MPs appeared, active within the framework of Islamic discourse [Sadeghi, 2021, p. 328].

The 21st century has seen an increase in women's political activism in Iran. Although they still do not have access to the posts of president or supreme leader (*vali-ye faqih*), women occupy significant positions: members of the Majlis (parliament) – from 9 to 17 women at different times; deputy ministers (especially in the fields of education, science, and culture); presidential advisers on family and women's issues (for example, Shahindokht Movlaherdi in the 2010s); judges in some administrative and family courts; members of city councils and activists at the local level [Sadeghi, 2021. p. 331]. Iranian women are also active in social movements, including campaigns against violence, for the right to choose the form of hijab, and participation in cultural life and the blogosphere. University-educated women are especially active, many of whom have become symbols of social modernization in the Islamic context [Kian-Thiébaud, 2002, p. 104]. Iran ranks among the leaders in the Islamic world in terms of female education. More than 60% of university students are women, and this percentage continues to grow in graduate and postgraduate programs. Women are leaders in such sciences as medicine and pharmacy (up to 70% of graduates are women), engineering and IT (about 30-35% of students are women), humanities and languages (up to 75% women) [UNESCO, 2023, p. 4]. Iranian women include laureates of international awards, such as Maryam Mirzakhani, the first woman to be awarded the Fields Medal in Mathematics (2014) [Amanat & Vejdani, 2012, p. 233]. The role of women in Iran is a synthesis of tradition and modernity, Islamic worldview and the demands of globalization. Women have become bearers of a dual identity: religious and professional, traditional and innovative. Political activity and participation in science become a means of self-realization and cultural resistance, and not just social mobility. A woman in Iran is a philosophical subject, simultaneously being transformed and transforming society [Afary, 2009. p. 230].

Iranian Women in Diplomacy and International Relations: New Horizons of Public Service

For a long time, Iran's foreign policy, like most spheres of state power, remained an exclusively male space, especially in the first decades after the Islamic

Revolution. Women were relegated to a supporting role, often in the sphere of protocol and administrative functions in ministries.

However, since the late 1990s, especially during the reform era of Mohammad Khatami, there has been a gradual increase in the participation of women in the foreign policy system. With the support of progressive circles and the growing number of women with degrees in international relations, law, and political science, women began to occupy positions in the diplomatic corps [Kian-Thiébaud, 2002, p. 106]. One of the turning points was the appointment of Marzieh Afkham in 2013 as the official spokesperson of the Iranian Foreign Ministry, the first time in the history of the Islamic Republic that a woman became the public voice of the foreign policy department. She was later appointed Iran's ambassador to Malaysia, the first female ambassador since the Islamic Revolution [Afary, 2009, p. 241]. Fereshteh Hakkar is a diplomat and expert in international law; Leila Jonbeshi is Iran's ambassador to Finland; Women advisers in Iranian delegations to the UN, UNESCO, OSCE [UNESCO, 2023, p. 6]. As of 2023, there are more than 450 women working in the Iranian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, of which about 20 hold high diplomatic positions [Sadeghi, 2021, p. 336]. Women are actively involved in academic and cultural diplomacy, which is especially important for Iran's "soft power". Among them: teachers and researchers giving lectures at foreign universities; in particular, at universities in Central Asian countries. Representatives of Iran in cultural institutes (including the UNESCO Tehran Center). Participants in international forums dedicated to Islamic feminism, intercultural dialogue, and women's rights in Muslim countries [Amanat & Vejdani, 2012, p. 239]. Today, Iranian diplomacy relies on a "feminine strategy" of cultural influence, within which an educated Muslim woman becomes a symbol of an alternative model of modernity – not Western, but scientific, ethical and spiritually oriented. The participation of women in Iranian diplomacy is not only a political evolution, but also a manifestation of a new ontological status of women in the Islamic world. Here, women act as "translators of cultures," as subjects of transnational discourse, connecting East and West through a dialogue of values, and not through imitation. Iranian diplomatic practice demonstrates that interaction with the world can occur through a woman's presence without losing cultural identity. This is a challenge to the universalist concepts of secular feminism and a contribution to the diversity of global women's subjectivity [Keddie, 2003, p. 204].

The economic dimension is not limited to the exchange of goods. The economic dimension is expressed in the support of joint cultural and economic forums, the creation of conditions for business in the humanitarian sphere (translation activities, publishing, education). Iran strategically supports the spheres of cultural production - book publishing, translation, cinema, design, crafts. This is evident in joint exhibitions, cultural festivals and intellectual forums. However, as F. Khosrokhavar notes, "despite institutional efforts, Iran has not yet been able to build a sustainable economic model of cultural export to Uzbekistan" [Khosrokhavar, 2017, p. 49]. The economic component of Iranian soft power remains weak due to the limitations of the Iranian economy itself and the lack of a

clear strategy for economic presence in the region" [Khosrokhavar, 2017, p. 49]. The reason is the limitations of the private sector and the lack of flexible financial instruments in the cultural economy. The economic effectiveness of cultural policy remains limited and requires institutional renewal.

The spiritual dimension of Iran's cultural diplomacy is metaphysical and educational in nature. By promoting the legacy of philosophers such as Mulla Sadra, Ibn Sina and Sheikh Ahmad Ahsa'i, Iran seeks not only to broadcast culture, but to offer a holistic model of worldview. As S. Sharifi emphasizes, "Iran exports not just cultural forms, but a holistic system of coordinates based on the idea of a rational person and the harmony of the universe" [Sharifi, 2020, p. 45]. This strategy is marked by an attempt to contrast postmodern nihilism Eastern concept of meaning-centrism. The spiritual dimension, based on philosophical universalism, is the strongest side of the Iranian strategy, but it needs to be carefully adapted. However, tensions also appear here. According to T. Rakhmatov, "Iranian cultural diplomacy is vulnerable where it does not distinguish between spirituality and ideology" [Rakhmatov, 2021. p. 63]. Uzbek society, developing within the framework of secular statehood, demonstrates sensitivity to attempts to impose ideological values. Consequently, the philosophy of dialogue should become the basis of cultural diplomacy - with recognition of the right to otherness and a rejection of unification. Only the transition from cultural expansion to cultural dialogue will ensure Iran's sustainable influence in the context of cultural pluralism in Central Asia.

The socio-spiritual dimension is manifested in Iran's attempt to offer a model of Islamic identity that differs from the Arabic and Turkish versions. This is especially important in the context of the Central Asian countries' search for their own cultural paradigm. However, here Iran faces the challenges of limited interest in Shiite theology, wariness of politicized Islam, and competition from the Turkish model of pan-Turkism and secular humanism. The educational and scientific dimension plays an important role in cultural diplomacy. In recent years, Iran has focused on academic partnerships, postgraduate student exchanges, and support for oriental studies programs. For example, Iran finances the translation and publication of scientific literature in Persian and Uzbek. The universities of Tehran and Mashhad have opened courses on Central Asian culture and languages. As F. Mahdavi notes, "education is becoming Iran's main channel of strategic influence, allowing the creation of communities of experts sympathetic to the Iranian model of cultural development" [Mahdavi, 2022, p. 106]. In addition, Iran is increasingly using digital technologies as part of cultural diplomacy. Online platforms for learning the Persian language are being created, virtual conferences are being launched, as well as cultural podcasts and video channels. According to Z. Sadeghi, "Iran's digital diplomacy is aimed at reaching young people who are excluded from traditional diplomatic formats, but are actively included in the global media space" [Sadeghi, 2023. p. 51]. These new formats are especially effective in Uzbekistan, where the younger generation is increasingly consuming information through digital media. The modern education system of the Islamic

Republic of Iran is not only an institution for training personnel, but also an essential tool for cultural diplomacy and the transmission of national ideology. The country's education system is based on Islamic and Persian values, historically dating back to the Islamic Golden Age, when Iranian thinkers such as Abu Ali ibn Sina and al-Farabi became symbols of the synthesis of science and faith [Nasr, 1968, p. 17].

Iran's education system consists of the following levels:

Pre-school education - from 1 to 6 years;

Primary education - from 6 to 12 years;

Secondary education - from 12 to 18 years, divided into basic and specialized levels;

Higher education - includes bachelor's degree (4 years), master's degree (2 years), doctoral degree (3-5 years), as well as postgraduate and theological programs. As of 2024, there are more than 2,500 higher education institutions in Iran, including about 150 public universities, more than 500 private universities, and an extensive network of theological schools (hauzas), especially in the cities of Qom and Mashhad [Sadeghi, 2021, p. 321].

Since the 2010s, digital transformation programs for education have been actively implemented in Iran. The National Electronic Learning Platform (Shad) has been created, which is used for distance learning for schoolchildren and students. Online universities are also developing, including branches of the Islamic Free University and the Sharif University of Technology. Digital education contributes to a wider coverage of the rural population and women [Amanat & Vejdani, 2012. p. 226]. The Iranian government views digitalization not only as a technological process, but also as a way to integrate Islamic pedagogy with modern teaching methods, where moral education, digital etiquette, and ideological monitoring occupy a special place [Keddie, 2003, p. 198]. Iran demonstrates one of the highest rates of female participation in higher education among Islamic countries. As of 2024, women make up more than 60% of students in the country's universities [Keddie, 2003, p. 200]. In some areas, such as medicine, pharmacology, linguistics and pedagogy, this figure reaches 70%. This indicates a socio-cultural transformation in which female education has become a factor in the development of social modernization while maintaining Islamic identity. Thus, women's education in Iran is simultaneously a form of social emancipation and cultural consolidation [Sadeghi, 2021. p. 324]. Education in Iran performs not only utilitarian functions, but also a philosophical and spiritual mission, forming a personality type that combines scientific thinking, Islamic worldview and national identity. In this sense, it becomes an element of spiritual resistance to globalization and cultural expansion, continuing the traditions of intellectual independence and scientific research characteristic of Iranian civilization [Nasr, 1968, p. 22].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the analysis shows that Iran's cultural diplomacy in Central Asia, particularly in Uzbekistan, has a historically rooted and rich in content basis, but

faces certain limitations. Comparing the approaches of researchers, it can be noted that: Iranian cultural diplomacy in Central Asia is a flexible and multi-layered instrument based on a rich tradition, but in need of adaptation to the new realities of the region. Today, Iran's cultural diplomacy in the countries of Central Asia is not only an instrument of "soft power", but also a deep philosophical phenomenon reflecting the desire for inter-civilizational dialogue, historical memory and humanistic rapprochement. As the analysis shows, Iranian cultural expansion is carried out not through dominance, but through symbolic communication appealing to common origins, the Iranian cultural code and the Islamic intellectual heritage, which has had a powerful influence on the development of the Turkic-Muslim civilization. Politically, Iran does not seek to interfere, but to strengthen ties through cultural involvement. Its policy in the region is based on the principles of non-violent influence, dialogue of traditions and respect for sovereignty. In the context of global geopolitical transformation, Iran offers Central Asia an alternative paradigm of dialogue, in which not only political and economic interests are important, but also the spiritual and philosophical foundations of interaction.

Economically, Iran's cultural diplomacy is manifested in strengthening humanitarian ties: student exchanges, academic projects, joint publications, the creation of Iranian cultural centers. These steps form a soft institutional infrastructure of cooperation, which in the future can support stronger economic alliances. Culturally, Central Asia and Iran have a common civilizational archive - from Persian classical literature and philosophy to a common Islamic heritage. This serves as a basis for cultural empathy and mutual understanding, especially among intellectual and religious elites. Through the revival of cultural memory and shared values (justice, spirituality, respect for knowledge), a new model of regional identity is being formed - open, pluralistic and based on mutual respect. Socially, Iranian cultural diplomacy stimulates the development of intercultural tolerance and forms a sustainable interest in the "South-South" dialogue in Central Asia, especially among young people and academic circles. It promotes reflection on the historical past, understanding Islamic modernization and searching for their own development paths outside the Western imperative. Thus, Iran's influence on Central Asian countries through cultural diplomacy is not limited to traditional geopolitical categories. It is rooted in philosophical and cultural interaction, where the central place is occupied by value rapprochement and the search for the spiritual integrity of the region. Cultural diplomacy is becoming not just a means of foreign policy, but also a vector for the revival of civilizational dialogue, capable of strengthening sustainable regional cooperation based on common semantic coordinates.

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